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A Creative Folio

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What you are, I was; What I am, you'll be

(A Villanelle)

What you are, I was; What I am, you'll be
Many are waiting, many are in queue
To follow affliction; to follow me

Here, there's no light, no eternity
Here, I am the judge; you cannot sue
What You are, I was; What I am, you'll be

Here only lies your greatest tragedy
I am not your dear friend; I am your foe
To follow affliction; to follow me

Here, there's no sun; here, you cannot see
Here, you find yourself in vanity
What You are, I was; What I am, You'll be

Do you not believe me? Just wait and see
You chose this fate; now face what you owe
To follow affliction; to follow me

You damn braggart! Do not ever dare me
You challenged Hades; now face what you owe
What you are, I was; What I am, you'll be
To follow affliction; to follow me